

4–Remainder Cordial of Some Tree Related Graphs

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Abstract: Let G be a (p, q) graph. Let f be a map from $V(G)$ to the set $\{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ where k is an integer $2 < k \leq |V(G)|$. For each edge uv assign the label r where r is the remainder when $f(u)$ is divided by $f(v)$ (or) $f(v)$ is divided by $f(u)$ according as $f(u) \geq f(v)$ or $f(v) \geq f(u)$. The function f is called a k -remainder cordial labeling of G if $|v_f(i) - v_f(j)| \leq 1$, $i, j \in \{1, \dots, k\}$ where $v_f(x)$ denote the number of vertices labelled with x and $|\eta_o - \eta_e| \leq 1$ where η_e and η_o respectively denote the number of edges labeled with even integers and number of edges labelled with odd integers. A graph with a k -remainder cordial labeling is called a k -remainder cordial graph. In this paper we investigate the 4–remainder cordial labeling behavior of banana tree, coconut tree, bamboo tree.

Key Words: Tree, banana tree, coconut tree, double coconut tree, bamboo tree, k -remainder cordial labeling, Smarandachely k -remainder cordial labeling.

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§1. Introduction

All graphs in this paper are finite, undirected and simple. The vertex set and edge set of a graph are denoted by $V(G)$ and $E(G)$ respectively. Ponraj et al. defined the k -remainder cordial labeling of a graph in [3]. k -Remainder cordial labeling behavior of path, cycle, star, complete graph, wheel, comb etc have been investigated in [3]. Here we investigate the 4-Remainder cordial labeling behavior of Banana tree, Coconut tree, Double coconut tree, Bamboo tree, caterpillar tree.

§2. 4- Remainder Cordial Labeling

Definition 2.1 Let G be a (p, q) graph. Let f be a map from $V(G)$ to the set $\{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ where k is an integer $2 < k \leq |V(G)|$. For each edge uv assign the label r where r is the remainder when $f(u)$ is divided by $f(v)$ (or) $f(v)$ is divided by $f(u)$ according as $f(u) \geq f(v)$ or $f(v) \geq f(u)$. The function f is called a k -remainder cordial labeling of G if $|v_f(i) - v_f(j)| \leq 1$,

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$i, j \in \{1, \dots, k\}$ where $v_f(x)$ denote the number of vertices labelled with x and $|\eta_e - \eta_o| \leq 1$ where η_e and η_o respectively denote the number of edges labeled with even integers and number of edges labelled with odd integers. A graph with a k -remainder cordial labeling is called a k -remainder cordial graph.

Conversely, the function f is called a Smarandachely k -remainder cordial labeling of G if there an integer pair $\{i, j\} \subset \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ with $|v_f(i) - v_f(j)| > 1$ and $|\eta_e - \eta_o| \leq 1$. Such a graph with a Smarandachely k -remainder cordial labeling is called a Smarandachely k -remainder cordial graph.

Definition 2.2 The banana tree $B(m, n)$ is a graph obtained by connecting one leaf of each of m - copies of the star $K_{1,n}$ with a single root vertex that is distinct from all the stars.

Definition 2.3 The coconut tree $CT(m, n)$ is a graph obtained from the path P_n by appending m new pendent edges at an end vertex of P_n .

Definition 2.4 The double Coconut tree $DCT(m, n, r)$ is a tree obtained by attaching $m > 1$ pendent vertices to one end of the path P_n and $r > 1$ pendent vertices to the other end of P_n .

Definition 2.5 The fire cracker $F_{n,k}$ is obtained by the concatenation of n - copies of k -stars by linking one leaf from each.

Definition 2.6 The bamboo tree $BT(n, m, k)$ is a tree obtained from k copies of paths P_n of length $n - 1$ and $K_{1,m}$ stars. Identify one of the two pendant vertices of the j^{th} path with centre of the j^{th} star. Identify the other pendant vertex of a each path with a single vertex u_0 .

Definition 2.7 The caterpillar $S_n(m_1, m_2, \dots, m_n)$ is a tree obtained from the path $u_1 u_2 \dots u_n$ by identifying the centre of the star K_{1,m_i} , ($1 \leq i \leq n$) with u_i . And let the vertex set and edge set of star K_{1,m_i} be

$$V(K_{1,m_i}) = \{v_i, u_{i,j} : 1 \leq i \leq n, 1 \leq j \leq m\}, \quad E(K_{1,m_i}) = \{v_i u_{i,j} : 1 \leq i \leq n, 1 \leq j \leq m\},$$

identifying u_i with v_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$).

§3. Main Results

Theorem 3.1 The banana tree $B(m, n)$ is 4–remainder cordial for $m \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$ and n is any positive integer.

Proof Let the vertex set and edge set of $B(m, n)$ be

$$\begin{aligned} V(B(m, n)) &= \{a_1, a_{i,1}, a_{i,2}, \dots, a_{i,m} : 1 \leq i \leq n\}, \\ E(B(m, n)) &= \{a_1 a_{1,i}, a_{1,i} a_{2,i} : 1 \leq i \leq m\} \cup \{a_{2,j} a_{i,j} : 3 \leq i \leq n, 1 \leq j \leq m\}. \end{aligned}$$

First, assign the label 3 to the vertex a_1 which has degree n . Next assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $a_{1,i}$ ($1 \leq i \leq 4$) which has degree 2 and assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4

respectively to the vertices $a_{1,i}$ ($5 \leq i \leq 8$) which has degree 2. Proceeding like this until we reach the vertex $a_{1,m}$.

Next, move to the vertices which has degree $n - 1$. Define

$$f(a_{2,i}) = \begin{cases} 2 & \text{if } f(a_{1,i}) = 1, \\ 3 & \text{if } f(a_{1,i}) = 2, \\ 4 & \text{if } f(a_{1,i}) = 3, \\ 1 & \text{if } f(a_{1,i}) = 4. \end{cases}$$

Finally, move to the pendant vertices. Assign the labels to the vertices $f(a_{i,j})$, ($(1 \leq j \leq m)$ and $(3 \leq i \leq n)$) by

$$f(a_{i,j}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } f(a_{1,i}) = 1, \\ 2 & \text{if } f(a_{1,i}) = 3, \\ 3 & \text{if } f(a_{1,i}) = 2, \\ 4 & \text{if } f(a_{1,i}) = 4. \end{cases}$$

Thus, this vertex labeling shows that f is the 4-remainder cordial labeling of $B(m, n)$ for $m \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$. Since $v_f(1) = v_f(2) = v_f(4) = \frac{mn}{4}$, $v_f(3) = \frac{mn+4}{4}$ and $\eta_e = \eta_o = \frac{mn}{2}$. This completes the proof. \square

A 4-remainder cordial labeling of $B(4, 5)$ is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Theorem 3.2 *The coconut tree $CT(n, n)$ is 4-remainder cordial for all values of n .*

Proof Let P_n be the path $v_1v_2 \cdots v_n$ and let $V(K_{1,n}) = \{w, w_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ are the vertex set of $CT(n, n)$ and edge set $E(CT(n, n)) = E(P_n) \cup E(K_{1,n})$ identifying the w with v_n . The proof of this theorem this proved in the following four cases.

Case 1. $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

First, assign the label to the vertices of the path P_n . Assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4 and assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices v_5, v_6, v_7, v_8 . Next assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $v_9, v_{10}, v_{11}, v_{12}$. Proceeding

like this until we reach the vertex v_{n-4} and assign the labels 1, 1, 2, 3 respectively to the vertices $v_{n-3}, v_{n-2}, v_{n-1}, v_n$.

Next, move to the vertices of the star $K_{1,n}$. Assign the label 1 to the vertices $w_1, w_5, w_9, \dots, w_{n-7}$ and assign the label 2 to the vertices $w_2, w_6, w_{10}, \dots, w_{n-6}$. Secondly assign the label 3 to the vertices $w_3, w_7, w_{11}, w_{n-5}$ and assign the label 4 to the vertices $w_4, w_8, w_{12}, \dots, w_{n-4}$. Finally assign the labels 2, 3, 4, 4 respectively to the vertices $w_{n-3}, w_{n-2}, w_{n-1}, w_n$.

Case 2. $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

First, assign the label to the vertices of the path P_n . Assign the label 1 to the vertices $v_1, v_5, v_9, \dots, v_{n-4}$ and assign the label 2 to the vertices $v_2, v_6, v_{10}, \dots, v_{n-3}$. Secondly assign the label 3 to the vertices $v_3, v_7, v_{11}, \dots, v_{n-2}$ and assign the label 4 to the vertices $v_4, v_8, v_{12}, \dots, v_{n-1}$. Finally assign the labels 3 to the vertex v_n .

Next, move to the vertices of the star $K_{1,n}$. Assign the label 1 to the vertices $w_4, w_8, w_{12}, \dots, w_{n-5}$ and assign the label 2 to the vertices $w_5, w_9, w_{13}, \dots, w_{n-4}$. Secondly assign the label 3 to the vertices $w_6, w_{10}, w_{14}, \dots, w_{n-3}$ and assign the label 4 to the vertices $w_7, w_{11}, w_{15}, \dots, w_{n-2}$. Finally assign the label 1 to the vertices w_1 and w_{n-1} and assign the label 3 to the vertex w_2 then assign the label 4 to the vertex w_3 and assign the label 2 to the vertex w_n .

Case 3. $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

First, assign the label to the vertices of the path P_n . Assign the label 1 to the vertices $v_1, v_5, v_9, \dots, v_{n-5}$ and assign the label 2 to the vertices $v_2, v_6, v_{10}, \dots, v_{n-4}$. Secondly assign the label 3 to the vertices $v_3, v_7, v_{11}, \dots, v_{n-3}$ and assign the label 4 to the vertices $v_4, v_8, v_{12}, \dots, v_{n-2}$. Finally assign the labels 1, 3 respectively to the vertices v_{n-1}, v_n .

Next, assign the labels to the vertices of the star $K_{1,n}$. Assign the label 1 to the vertices $w_4, w_8, w_{12}, \dots, w_{n-6}$ and assign the label 2 to the vertices $w_5, w_9, w_{13}, \dots, w_{n-5}$. Secondly, assign the label 3 to the vertices $w_6, w_{10}, w_{14}, \dots, w_{n-4}$ and assign the label 4 to the vertices $w_7, w_{11}, w_{15}, \dots, w_{n-3}$. Finally, assign the label 1 to the vertex w_1 and assign the label 2 to the vertices w_2 and w_{n-2} , then assign the label 3 to the vertex w_{n-1} and assign the labels 4 to the vertices w_3 and w_n .

Case 4. $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

First, assign the labels to the vertices of the path P_n . Assign the label 1 to the vertices $v_1, v_5, v_9, \dots, v_{n-2}$ and assign the label 2 to the vertices $v_2, v_6, v_{10}, \dots, v_{n-1}$. Secondly, assign the label 3 to the vertices $v_3, v_7, v_{11}, \dots, v_n$ and assign the label 4 to the vertices $v_4, v_8, v_{12}, \dots, v_{n-3}$.

Next, assign the labels to the vertices of the star $K_{1,n}$. Assign the label 1 to the vertices $w_2, w_6, w_{10}, \dots, w_{n-1}$ and assign the label 2 to the vertices $w_3, w_7, w_{11}, \dots, w_n$. Secondly assign the label 3 to the vertices $w_4, w_8, w_{12}, \dots, w_{n-3}$ and assign the label 4 to the vertices $w_5, w_9, w_{13}, \dots, w_{n-2}$. Finally, assign the labels 4 to the vertex w_1 and assign the labels 1, 2 to the vertices w_{n-1}, w_n .

Thus, the Table 1 given below shows that coconut tree graph admits the 4-remainder cordial labeling.

Nature of n	$v_f(1)$	$v_f(2)$	$v_f(3)$	$v_f(4)$	η_e	η_o
$n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{n}{2}$	$\frac{n}{2}$	$\frac{n}{2}$	$\frac{n}{2}$	$n - 1$	n
$n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{n+1}{2}$	$\frac{n-1}{2}$	$\frac{n+1}{2}$	$\frac{n-1}{2}$	$n - 1$	n
$n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{n}{2}$	$\frac{n}{2}$	$\frac{n}{2}$	$\frac{n}{2}$	$n - 1$	n
$n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{n+1}{2}$	$\frac{n+1}{2}$	$\frac{n-1}{2}$	$\frac{n-1}{2}$	$n - 1$	n

Table 1.

This completes the proof. □

A 4-remainder cordial labeling of $CT(6, 6)$ is given in Figure 2.

Figure 2

Theorem 3.3 A double coconut tree $DCT(n, n, n)$ is 4-remainder cordial for all values of n .

Proof Let P_n be the path $w_1 w_2 \cdots w_n$ and $V(DCT(n, n, n)) = V(P_n) \cup \{u_i, v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and $E(DCT(n, n, n)) = E(P_n) \cup \{v_i w_1 : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{u_i w_n : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$. Clearly $DCT(n, n, n)$ has $3n$ vertices and $3n - 1$ edges.

Now we describe the vertex labeling as follows. There are four cases arise.

Case 1. $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

First, assign the label to the vertices of the path P_n . Assign the label 3, 2 to the vertices w_1, w_2 and assign the label 2, 3 to the vertices w_{n-1}, w_n . Next assign the label 1, 2, 3, 4 to the vertices w_3, w_4, w_5, w_6 and assign the label 1, 2, 3, 4 to the vertices w_7, w_8, w_9, w_{10} . Proceeding like this until we reach w_{n-2} .

Next, assign the labels for the pendent vertices. First, assign the label 3 to the vertex u_{n-3} and then assign the labels 4 to the vertices u_{n-2}, u_{n-1}, u_n . Secondly assign the label 2 to the vertex v_{n-3} and then assign the labels 1 to the vertices v_{n-2}, v_{n-1}, v_n . Next assign the labels for the remaining vertices. Assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 to the vertices u_i and v_i ($3 \leq i \leq 6$). Then assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 to the vertices u_i and v_i ($7 \leq i \leq 10$). Proceeding like this until we reach u_{n-4} and v_{n-4} .

Case 2. $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

First, assign the label to the vertices of the path P_n . Assign the label 3, 2 to the vertices

w_1, w_2 and assign the label 4, 2, 3 to the vertices w_{n-2}, w_{n-1}, w_n . Next assign the label 1, 2, 3, 4 to the vertices w_3, w_4, w_5, w_6 and assign the label 1, 2, 3, 4 to the vertices w_7, w_8, w_9, w_{10} . Proceeding like this until we reach w_{n-3} .

Next, assign the labels for the pendent vertices. First assign the label 3 to the vertex u_{n-4}, u_{n-3} and then assign the label 4 to the vertices u_{n-2}, u_{n-1}, u_n . Secondly assign the label 2 to the vertex v_{n-4}, v_{n-3} and then assign the labels 1 to the vertices v_{n-2}, v_{n-1}, v_n . Next assign the labels for the remaining vertices. Assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 to the vertices u_i and v_i ($3 \leq i \leq 6$). Then assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 to the vertices u_i and v_i ($7 \leq i \leq 10$). Proceeding like this until we reach u_{n-5} and v_{n-5} .

Case 3. $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

First, assign the label to the vertices of the path P_n . Assign the label 3, 2 to the vertices w_1, w_2 . Next assign the label 1, 2, 3, 4 to the vertices w_3, w_4, w_5, w_6 and assign the label 1, 2, 3, 4 to the vertices w_7, w_8, w_9, w_{10} . Proceeding like this until we reach w_n .

Next, assign the labels for the pendent vertices. First assign the label 3 to the vertices $u_i, (i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n}{2})$ which is adjacent with the vertex w_n and assign the label 2 to the vertices $u_i, (i = \frac{n+2}{2}, \frac{n+4}{2}, \dots, n)$ which is adjacent with vertex w_n . Next assign the labels 4 to the vertices $v_i, (i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n}{2})$ which is adjacent with the vertex w_1 and then assign the label 1 to the vertices $v_i, (i = \frac{n+2}{2}, \frac{n+4}{2}, \dots, n)$ which is adjacent with vertex w_1 .

Case 4. $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

First, assign the label to the vertices of the path P_n . Assign the label 3, 2 to the vertices w_1, w_2 . Next assign the label 1, 2, 3, 4 to the vertices w_3, w_4, w_5, w_6 and assign the label 1, 2, 3, 4 to the vertices w_7, w_8, w_9, w_{10} . Proceeding like this until we reach w_{n-1} . Next assign the label 4 to the vertex w_n .

Next, assign the labels for the pendent vertices. First assign the label 3 to the vertices $u_i, (i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n+1}{2})$ which is adjacent with the vertex w_n and assign the label 2 to the vertices $u_i, (i = \frac{n+3}{2}, \frac{n+5}{2}, \dots, n)$ which is adjacent with vertex w_n . Next assign the labels 1 to the vertices $v_i, (i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n+1}{2})$ which is adjacent with the vertex w_1 and then assign the label 4 to the vertices $v_i, (i = \frac{n+3}{2}, \frac{n+5}{2}, \dots, n)$ which is adjacent with vertex w_1 .

Thus, the Table 2 given below shows that the double coconut tree graph admits the 4-remainder cordial.

Nature of n	$v_f(1)$	$v_f(2)$	$v_f(3)$	$v_f(4)$	η_e	η_o
$n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{3n}{4}$	$\frac{3n}{4}$	$\frac{3n}{4}$	$\frac{3n}{4}$	$\frac{3n-2}{2}$	$\frac{3n}{2}$
$n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{3n-3}{4}$	$\frac{3n+1}{4}$	$\frac{3n+1}{4}$	$\frac{3n+1}{4}$	$\frac{3n-1}{2}$	$\frac{3n-1}{2}$
$n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{3n-2}{4}$	$\frac{3n+2}{4}$	$\frac{3n+2}{4}$	$\frac{3n-2}{4}$	$\frac{3n-2}{2}$	$\frac{3n}{2}$
$n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{3n-1}{4}$	$\frac{3n-1}{4}$	$\frac{3n+3}{4}$	$\frac{3n-1}{4}$	$\frac{3n-1}{2}$	$\frac{3n-1}{2}$

Table 2

This completes the proof. □

Theorem 3.4 *The fire cracker $F_{n,k}$ is 4- remainder cordial for all values of n .*

Proof Let $V(F_{n,k}) = \{v_o^i, v_1^i, v_2^i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ where v_o^i be the apex vertices of the star and $E(F_{n,k}) = \{v_o^i v_1^j : 1 \leq i \leq n, 1 \leq j \leq 2\} \cup \{v_o^i v_o^{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\}$. Clearly G has $3n$ vertices and $3n-1$ edges.

Now we describe the vertex labeling. There are four cases arises.

Case 1. $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

First, assign the labels for the vertices v_o^i . Assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $v_o^1, v_o^2, v_o^3, v_o^4$ and assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $v_o^5, v_o^6, v_o^7, v_o^8$. Next assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $v_o^9, v_o^{10}, v_o^{11}, v_o^{12}$. Proceeding like this until we reach v_o^n . In similar way assign the labels for v_2^i , ($1 \leq i \leq n$). Next assign the labels for v_1^i , assign the labels 4, 3, 2, 1 respectively to the vertices $v_1^1, v_1^2, v_1^3, v_1^4$ and assign the labels 4, 3, 2, 1 respectively to the vertices $v_1^5, v_1^6, v_1^7, v_1^8$ and then assign the labels 4, 3, 2, 1 respectively to the vertices $v_1^9, v_1^{10}, v_1^{11}, v_1^{12}$. Proceeding like this until we reach v_1^n .

Case 2. $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

As in Case 1, assign the labels for the vertices v_o^i, v_1^i, v_2^i ($1 \leq i \leq n-1$). Finally assign the label 1 to the vertex v_o^n and assign the label 2 to the vertex v_1^n , then assign the label 3 to the vertex v_2^n .

Case 3. $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

As in Case 1, assign the labels for the vertices v_o^i, v_1^i, v_2^i ($1 \leq i \leq n-2$). Finally assign the label 1 to the vertex v_o^{n-1} and assign the label 2 to the vertex v_o^n , then assign the label 2 to the vertex v_1^{n-1} and assign the label 3 to the vertex v_1^n . Next assign the label 3 to the vertex v_2^{n-1} and assign the label 4 to the vertex v_2^n .

Case 4. $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

As in Case 1, assign the labels for the vertices v_o^i, v_1^i ($1 \leq i \leq n$) and v_2^i ($1 \leq i \leq n-1$). Note that in this process the vertex v_o^{n-2} and v_2^{n-2} gets the label 1, and the vertex v_o^{n-1} and v_2^{n-1} gets the label 2, the vertex v_o^n gets the label 3 and the vertex v_1^{n-2} get the label 4. Next the vertex v_1^{n-1} get the label 3 and to the vertex v_1^n get the label 2. Finally assign the label 4 to the vertex v_2^n .

Thus, the Table 3 below shows that this vertex labeling gives the 4-remainder cordial labeling of fire cracker.

Nature of n	$v_f(1)$	$v_f(2)$	$v_f(3)$	$v_f(4)$	η_e	η_o
$n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{3n}{4}$	$\frac{3n}{4}$	$\frac{3n}{4}$	$\frac{3n}{4}$	$\frac{3n-2}{2}$	$\frac{3n}{2}$
$n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{3n+1}{4}$	$\frac{3n+1}{4}$	$\frac{3n+1}{4}$	$\frac{3n-3}{4}$	$\frac{3n-1}{2}$	$\frac{3n-1}{2}$
$n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{3n-2}{4}$	$\frac{3n+2}{4}$	$\frac{3n+2}{4}$	$\frac{3n-2}{4}$	$\frac{3n-2}{2}$	$\frac{3n}{2}$
$n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{3n-1}{4}$	$\frac{3n+3}{4}$	$\frac{3n-1}{4}$	$\frac{3n-1}{4}$	$\frac{3n-1}{2}$	$\frac{3n-1}{2}$

Table 3

This completes the proof. \square

Theorem 3.5 *The bamboo tree $BT(n, n, n)$ is 4-remainder cordial for $n \equiv 0, 2 \pmod{4}$.*

Proof Let

$$\begin{aligned} V(BT(n, n, n)) &= \{u_o, u_{i,j}, w_{i,i} : 1 \leq i \leq n, 1 \leq j \leq n-1\}, \\ E(BT(n, n, n)) &= \{u_o u_{i,1}, u_{i,n-1} w_{i,i} : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{u_{i,i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-2\} \end{aligned}$$

We prove this theorem in two cases.

Case 1. $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

First, assign the label 3 to the vertex u_o . Let $f : V \rightarrow \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ defined by

$$f(u_{i,1}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for all } i = 1, 5, 9, \dots, i+4, \dots, n-3, \\ 2 & \text{for all } i = 2, 6, 10, \dots, i+4, \dots, n-2, \\ 3 & \text{for all } i = 3, 7, 11, \dots, i+4, \dots, n-1, \\ 4 & \text{for all } i = 4, 8, 12, \dots, i+4, \dots, n. \end{cases}$$

Next, assign the labels for the vertices of the paths. Consider the path P_1, P_5, \dots, P_{n-3} . Assign the labels 4, 1, 4, 1, \dots , 4, 1 consecutively to the vertices of this paths. Next consider the paths P_2, P_6, \dots, P_{n-2} . Assign the labels 3, 2, 3, 2, \dots , 3, 2 consecutively to the vertices of these paths. Next consider the paths P_3, P_7, \dots, P_{n-1} . Assign the labels 2, 3, 2, 3, \dots , 2, 3 consecutively to the vertices of these paths, lastly consider the paths P_4, P_8, \dots, P_n . Assign the labels 1, 4, 1, 4, \dots , 1, 4 consecutively to the vertices of these paths.

And then, move to the vertices of the star. Assign the label 1 to the vertices $w_{i,i}$, ($1 \leq i \leq n$) if $u_{i,n-1}$, ($1 \leq i \leq n$) gets label 1. Secondly assign the label 3 to the vertices $w_{i,i}$, ($1 \leq i \leq n$) if $u_{i,n-1}$, ($1 \leq i \leq n$) gets label 2. Then assign the label 2 to the vertices $w_{i,i}$, ($1 \leq i \leq n$) if $u_{i,n-1}$, ($1 \leq i \leq n$) gets label 3. Finally assign the label 4 to the vertices $w_{i,i}$, ($1 \leq i \leq n$) if $u_{i,n-1}$, ($1 \leq i \leq n$) gets label 4.

Case 2. $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

First assign the label 3 to the vertex u_o . Define

$$f(u_{i,1}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for all } i = 1, 5, 9, \dots, i+4, \dots, n-1, \\ 2 & \text{for all } i = 2, 6, 10, \dots, i+4, \dots, n, \\ 3 & \text{for all } i = 3, 7, 11, \dots, i+4, \dots, n-3, \\ 4 & \text{for all } i = 4, 8, 12, \dots, i+4, \dots, n-2. \end{cases}$$

As in Case 1 assign the labels to the vertices of paths $u_{i,i+1}$, ($1 \leq i \leq n$) and the vertices of the stars $w_{i,i}$, ($1 \leq i \leq n-2$). Finally assign the label 1 to the vertices $w_{n-1,i}$, $1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2}$ if $f(u_{i,n-1}) = 2$ and assign the label 2 to the vertices $w_{n-1,i}$, $\frac{n+2}{2} \leq i \leq n$ if $f(u_{i,n-1}) = 1$, then assign the label 4 to the vertices $w_{n,i}$, $1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2}$ if $f(u_{i,n-1}) = 2$ and assign the label 3 to the vertices $w_{n,i}$, $\frac{n+2}{2} \leq i \leq n$ if $f(u_{i,n-1}) = 2$.

Thus, the Table 4 below shows that this vertex labeling gives the 4-remainder cordial

labeling of bamboo tree.

Nature of n	$v_f(1)$	$v_f(2)$	$v_f(3)$	$v_f(4)$	η_e	η_o
$n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{2n^2-n}{4}$	$\frac{2n^2-n}{4}$	$\frac{2n^2-n+2}{4}$	$\frac{2n^2-n}{4}$	$\frac{2n^2-n}{2}$	$\frac{2n^2-n}{2}$
$n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{2n^2-n+2}{4}$	$\frac{2n^2-n+2}{4}$	$\frac{2n^2-n+2}{4}$	$\frac{2n^2-n-2}{4}$	$\frac{2n^2-n}{2}$	$\frac{2n^2-n}{2}$

Table 4

This completes the proof. □

A 4-remainder cordial labeling of bamboo tree is given in Figure 3.

Figure 3

Theorem 3.6 *The caterpillar $S_n(m, m, \dots, m)$ is 4- remainder cordial for all values of n .*

Proof Taking the vertex set and edge set is of $S_n(m, m, \dots, m)$ as in Definition 2.8. We prove this theorem in two cases.

Case 1. $m = n$.

Subcase 1.1 $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

First, assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4 and assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices u_5, u_6, u_7, u_8 . Next assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $u_9, u_{10}, u_{11}, u_{12}$. Proceeding like this until we reach the vertices $u_{n-3}, u_{n-2}, u_{n-1}, u_n$.

Next, assign the label to the pendent vertices $u_{i,j}$ ($1 \leq i, j \leq n$) by

$$f(u_{i,j}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 1, } i = 1, 5, 9, \dots, n-3, \\ 2 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 3, } i = 2, 6, 10, \dots, n-2, \\ 3 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 2, } i = 3, 7, 11, \dots, n-1, \\ 4 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 4, } i = 4, 8, 12, \dots, n. \end{cases}$$

Subcase 1.1 $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

First, assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4 and assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices u_5, u_6, u_7, u_8 . Next assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $u_9, u_{10}, u_{11}, u_{12}$. Proceeding like this until we assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 to the vertices $u_{n-4}, u_{n-3}, u_{n-2}, u_{n-1}$ and then assign the label 3 to the vertex u_n .

Next, assign the label to the pendent vertices $u_{i,j}$ ($1 \leq i, j \leq n$) by

$$f(u_{i,j}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 1, } i = 1, 5, 9, \dots, n-4, \\ 2 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 3, } i = 2, 6, 10, \dots, n-3, \\ 3 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 2, } i = 3, 7, 11, \dots, n-2, \\ 4 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 4, } i = 4, 8, 12, \dots, n-1. \end{cases}$$

Finally, assign the label 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $u_{n,1}, u_{n,2}, u_{n,3}, u_{n,4}$ and assign the label 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $u_{n,5}, u_{n,6}, u_{n,7}, u_{n,8}$. Proceeding like this until we reach the vertex $u_{n,(n-1)}$ then assign the label 1 to the vertex $u_{n,n}$.

Subcase 1.3 $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

First, assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4 and assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices u_5, u_6, u_7, u_8 . Next assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $u_9, u_{10}, u_{11}, u_{12}$. Proceeding like this until we assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 to the vertices $u_{n-5}, u_{n-4}, u_{n-3}, u_{n-2}$ and then assign the label 2, 3 to the vertices u_{n-1}, u_n .

Next, assign the label to the pendent vertices $u_{i,j}$ ($1 \leq i, j \leq n$) by

$$f(u_{i,j}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 1, } i = 1, 5, 9, \dots, n-5, \\ 2 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 3, } i = 2, 6, 10, \dots, n-4, \\ 3 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 2, } i = 3, 7, 11, \dots, n-3, \\ 4 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 4, } i = 4, 8, 12, \dots, n-2. \end{cases}$$

Finally, assign the label 1 to the vertices $u_{(n-1),i}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n}{2}$) and assign the label 2 to the vertices $u_{(n-1),i}$, ($i = \frac{n+2}{2}, \frac{n+4}{2}, \dots, n$). Then assign the label 3 to the vertices $u_{n,i}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n}{2}$) and then assign the label 4 to the vertices $u_{n,i}$, ($i = \frac{n+2}{2}, \frac{n+4}{2}, \dots, n$).

Subcase 1.4 $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

First, assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4 and assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices u_5, u_6, u_7, u_8 . Next assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $u_9, u_{10}, u_{11}, u_{12}$. Proceeding like this until we reach u_{n-3} , then assign the label 1, 2, 3 to the vertices u_{n-2}, u_{n-1}, u_n .

Next, assign the label to the pendent vertices $u_{i,j}$ ($1 \leq i, j \leq n$) by

$$f(u_{i,j}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 1, } i = 1, 5, 9, \dots, n-6, \\ 2 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 3, } i = 2, 6, 10, \dots, n-5, \\ 3 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 2, } i = 3, 7, 11, \dots, n-4, \\ 4 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 4, } i = 4, 8, 12, \dots, n-3. \end{cases}$$

Finally, assign the label 1 to the vertices $u_{(n-2),i}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{3n-1}{4}$) and assign the label 2 to the vertices $u_{(n-2),i}$, ($i = \frac{3n+3}{4}, \frac{3n+7}{4}, \dots, n$) and $u_{(n-1),i}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n-1}{2}$). Then assign the label 3 to the vertices $u_{(n-1),i}$, ($i = \frac{n+1}{2}, \frac{n+3}{2}, \dots, n$) and $u_{n,i}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{n-3}{4}$) and then assign the label 4 to the vertices $u_{n,i}$, ($i = \frac{n+1}{4}, \frac{n+5}{4}, \dots, n$).

Thus, the Table 5 below shows that this vertex labeling gives the 4-remainder cordial labeling of caterpillar.

Nature of n	$v_f(1)$	$v_f(2)$	$v_f(3)$	$v_f(4)$	η_e	η_o
$n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{n^2+n}{4}$	$\frac{n^2+n}{4}$	$\frac{n^2+n}{4}$	$\frac{n^2+n}{4}$	$\frac{n^2+n}{2}$	$\frac{n^2+n-2}{2}$
$n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{n^2+n+2}{4}$	$\frac{n^2+n-2}{4}$	$\frac{n^2+n+2}{4}$	$\frac{n^2+n-2}{4}$	$\frac{n^2+n-2}{2}$	$\frac{n^2+n}{2}$
$n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{n^2+n-2}{4}$	$\frac{n^2+n+2}{4}$	$\frac{n^2+n+2}{4}$	$\frac{n^2+n-2}{4}$	$\frac{n^2+n-2}{2}$	$\frac{n^2+n}{2}$
$n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{n^2+n}{4}$	$\frac{n^2+n}{4}$	$\frac{n^2+n}{4}$	$\frac{n^2+n}{4}$	$\frac{n^2+n-2}{2}$	$\frac{n^2+n}{2}$

Table 5

Case 2. $m \neq n$.

Subcase 2.1 $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}, m \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

As in Case 1 assign the label to the vertices u_i and $u_{i,j}$.

Subcase 2.2 $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}, m \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

As in Case 1 assign the label to the vertices u_i , $1 \leq i \leq n-5$ and assign the label 1, 3, 2, 4, 3 respectively to the vertices $u_{n-4}, u_{n-3}, u_{n-2}, u_{n-1}, u_n$. Next assign the labels to the vertices $u_{i,j}$ ($1 \leq i \leq n-1, 1 \leq j \leq m$) by

$$f(u_{i,j}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 1, } i = 1, 5, 9, \dots, n-4, \\ 2 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 3, } i = 2, 6, 10, \dots, n-3, \\ 3 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 2, } i = 3, 7, 11, \dots, n-2, \\ 4 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 4, } i = 4, 8, 12, \dots, n-1. \end{cases}$$

Finally, assign the label 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $u_{n,1}, u_{n,2}, u_{n,3}, u_{n,4}$ and assign the label 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $u_{n,5}, u_{n,6}, u_{n,7}, u_{n,8}$. Proceeding like this until we reach the vertex $u_{n,m}$.

Subcase 2.3 $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}, m \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

First, assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4 and assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices u_5, u_6, u_7, u_8 . Next assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $u_9, u_{10}, u_{11}, u_{12}$. Proceeding like this until we assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 to the vertices $u_{n-5}, u_{n-4}, u_{n-3}, u_{n-2}$ and then assign the label 1, 3 to the vertices u_{n-1}, u_n .

Next assign the label to the pendent vertices $u_{i,j}$ ($1 \leq i \leq n - 2, 1 \leq j \leq m$) by

$$f(u_{i,j}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label } 1, i = 1, 5, 9, \dots, n - 5, \\ 2 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label } 3, i = 2, 6, 10, \dots, n - 4, \\ 3 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label } 2, i = 3, 7, 11, \dots, n - 3, \\ 4 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label } 4, i = 4, 8, 12, \dots, n - 2. \end{cases}$$

Finally, assign the label 1 to the vertices $u_{(n-1),i}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{m}{2}$) and assign the label 3 to the vertices $u_{(n-1),i}$, ($i = \frac{m+2}{2}, \frac{m+4}{2}, \dots, m$). Then assign the label 2 to the vertices $u_{n,i}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{m}{2}$) and then assign the label 4 to the vertices $u_{n,i}$, ($i = \frac{m+2}{2}, \frac{m+4}{2}, \dots, m$).

Subcase 2.4 $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}, m \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

As in Case 1 assign the label to the vertices $u_i, 1 \leq i \leq n$ and then assign the label to the pendent vertices $u_{i,j}$ ($1 \leq i \leq n - 3, 1 \leq j \leq m$) by

$$f(u_{i,j}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label } 1, i = 1, 5, 9, \dots, n - 6, \\ 2 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label } 3, i = 2, 6, 10, \dots, n - 5, \\ 3 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label } 2, i = 3, 7, 11, \dots, n - 4, \\ 4 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label } 4, i = 4, 8, 12, \dots, n - 3. \end{cases}$$

Finally, assign the label 1 to the vertices $u_{(n-2),i}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{3m}{4}$) and assign the label 3 to the vertices $u_{(n-2),i}$, ($i = \frac{3m+4}{4}, \frac{3m+8}{4}, \dots, m$) and $u_{(n-1),i}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{m}{2}$). Then assign the label 2 to the vertices $u_{(n-1),i}$, ($i = \frac{m+2}{2}, \frac{m+4}{2}, \dots, m$) and $u_{n,i}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{m}{4}$) and then assign the label 4 to the vertices $u_{n,i}$, ($i = \frac{m+4}{4}, \frac{m+8}{4}, \dots, m$).

Thus, the Table 6 below shows that this vertex labeling gives the 4–remainder cordial labeling of caterpillar.

Nature of n	$v_f(1)$	$v_f(2)$	$v_f(3)$	$v_f(4)$	η_e	η_o
$n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-2}{2}$	$\frac{nm+n}{2}$
$n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-1}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n+3}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-1}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-1}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-2}{2}$	$\frac{nm+n}{2}$
$n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{nm+n+2}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-2}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n+2}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-2}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-1}{2}$	$\frac{nm+n-1}{2}$
$n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{nm+n+1}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n+1}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n+1}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-3}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-1}{2}$	$\frac{nm+n-1}{2}$

Table 6

Subcase 2.5 $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}, m \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

As in Case 1 assign the label to the vertices u_i and $u_{i,j}$.

Subcase 2.6 $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}, m \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

As in Case 1 assign the label to the vertices u_i and $u_{i,j}$.

Subcase 2.7 $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}, m \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

First, assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4 and assign the

labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices u_5, u_6, u_7, u_8 . Next assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $u_9, u_{10}, u_{11}, u_{12}$. Proceeding like this until we assign the labels 1, 2, 3, 4 to the vertices $u_{n-5}, u_{n-4}, u_{n-3}, u_{n-2}$ and then assign the label 2, 3 to the vertices u_{n-1}, u_n .

Next, assign the label to the pendent vertices $u_{i,j}$ ($1 \leq i \leq n-2, 1 \leq j \leq m$) by

$$f(u_{i,j}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 1, } i = 1, 5, 9, \dots, n-5, \\ 2 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 3, } i = 2, 6, 10, \dots, n-4, \\ 3 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 2, } i = 3, 7, 11, \dots, n-3, \\ 4 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 4, } i = 4, 8, 12, \dots, n-2. \end{cases}$$

Finally, assign the label 1 to the vertices $u_{(n-1),i}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{m+1}{2}$) and assign the label 3 to the vertices $u_{(n-1),i}$, ($i = \frac{m+3}{2}, \frac{m+5}{2}, \dots, m$). Then assign the label 2 to the vertices $u_{n,i}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{m-1}{2}$) and then assign the label 4 to the vertices $u_{n,i}$, ($i = \frac{m+1}{2}, \frac{m+3}{2}, \dots, m$).

Subcase 2.8 $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}, m \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

As in Case 1 assign the label to the vertices $u_i, 1 \leq i \leq n$ by

$$f(u_{i,j}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 1, } i = 1, 5, 9, \dots, n-6, \\ 2 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 3, } i = 2, 6, 10, \dots, n-5, \\ 3 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 2, } i = 3, 7, 11, \dots, n-4, \\ 4 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 4, } i = 4, 8, 12, \dots, n-3. \end{cases}$$

Finally, assign the label 1 to the vertices $u_{(n-2),i}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{m+1}{2}$) and assign the label 2 to the vertices $u_{(n-2),i}$, ($i = \frac{m+3}{2}, \frac{m+5}{2}, \dots, m$) and $u_{(n-1),i}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{m-1}{2}$). Then assign the label 3 to the vertices $u_{(n-1),i}$, ($i = \frac{m+1}{2}, \frac{m+3}{2}, \dots, m$) and $u_{n,i}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{m-1}{4}$) and then assign the label 4 to the vertices $u_{n,i}$, ($i = \frac{m+3}{4}, \frac{m+7}{4}, \dots, m$).

Thus, the Table 7 below shows that this vertex labeling gives the 4-remainder cordial labeling of caterpillar.

Nature of n	$v_f(1)$	$v_f(2)$	$v_f(3)$	$v_f(4)$	η_e	η_o
$n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{2}$	$\frac{nm+n-2}{2}$
$n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{nm+n+2}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-2}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n+2}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-2}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-2}{2}$	$\frac{nm+n}{2}$
$n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-1}{2}$	$\frac{nm+n-1}{2}$
$n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-2}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n+2}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n+2}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-2}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n+2}{2}$	$\frac{nm+n-2}{2}$

Table 7

Subcase 2.9 $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}, m \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

As in Case 1 assign the label to the vertices u_i and $u_{i,j}$.

Subcase 2.10 $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}, m \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

As in Case 1 assign the label to the vertices $u_i, 1 \leq i \leq n-5$ and assign the label 1, 3, 2, 4, 3

respectively to the vertices $u_{n-4}, u_{n-3}, u_{n-2}, u_{n-1}, u_n$. Next assign the labels to the vertices $u_{i,j}$ by

$$f(u_{i,j}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 1, } i = 1, 5, 9, \dots, n-4, \\ 2 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 3, } i = 2, 6, 10, \dots, n-2, \\ 3 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 2, } i = 3, 7, 11, \dots, n-3, \\ 4 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 4, } i = 4, 8, 12, \dots, n-1. \end{cases}$$

Finally, assign the label 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $u_{n,1}, u_{n,2}, u_{n,3}, u_{n,4}$ and assign the label 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $u_{n,5}, u_{n,6}, u_{n,7}, u_{n,8}$. Proceeding like this until we reach the vertex $u_{n,(m-2)}$ then finally assign the label 1, 2 to the vertices $u_{n,(m-1)}, u_{n,m}$.

Subcase 2.11 $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}, m \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

As in Case 1 assign the label to the vertices u_i and $u_{i,j}$.

Subcase 2.12 $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}, m \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

As in Case 1 assign the label to the vertices $u_i, 1 \leq i \leq n$ by

$$f(u_{i,j}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 1, } i = 1, 5, 9, \dots, n-6, \\ 2 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 3, } i = 2, 6, 10, \dots, n-5, \\ 3 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 2, } i = 3, 7, 11, \dots, n-4, \\ 4 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 4, } i = 4, 8, 12, \dots, n-3. \end{cases}$$

Finally, assign the label 1 to the vertices $u_{(n-2),i}, (i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{3m+2}{4})$ and assign the label 3 to the vertices $u_{(n-2),i}, (i = \frac{3m+6}{4}, \frac{3n+10}{4}, \dots, m)$ and $u_{(n-1),i}, (i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{m}{2})$. Then assign the label 2 to the vertices $u_{(n-1),i}, (i = \frac{m+2}{2}, \frac{m+4}{2}, \dots, m)$ and $u_{n,i}, (i = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{m+2}{4})$ and then assign the label 4 to the vertices $u_{n,i}, (i = \frac{m+6}{4}, \frac{m+10}{4}, \dots, m)$.

Thus, the Table 8 below shows that this vertex labeling gives the 4-remainder cordial labeling of caterpillar.

Nature of n	$v_f(1)$	$v_f(2)$	$v_f(3)$	$v_f(4)$	η_e	η_o
$n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-2}{2}$	$\frac{nm+n}{2}$
$n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{nm+n+1}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n+1}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n+1}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-3}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-1}{2}$	$\frac{nm+n-1}{2}$
$n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-2}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n+2}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n+2}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-2}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-2}{2}$	$\frac{nm+n}{2}$
$n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{nm+n+3}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-1}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-1}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-1}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-1}{2}$	$\frac{nm+n-1}{2}$

Table 8

Subcase 2.13 $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}, m \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

As in Case 1 assign the label to the vertices u_i and $u_{i,j}$.

Subcase 2.14 $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}, m \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

As in Case 1 assign the label to the vertices $u_i, 1 \leq i \leq n-5$ and assign the label 1, 3, 2, 4, 3 respectively to the vertices $u_{n-4}, u_{n-3}, u_{n-2}, u_{n-1}, u_n$. Next assign the labels to the vertices $u_{i,j}$

by

$$f(u_{i,j}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 1, } i = 1, 5, 9, \dots, n-4, \\ 2 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 3, } i = 2, 6, 10, \dots, n-2, \\ 3 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 2, } i = 3, 7, 11, \dots, n-3, \\ 4 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 4, } i = 4, 8, 12, \dots, n-1. \end{cases}$$

Finally, assign the label 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $u_{n,1}, u_{n,2}, u_{n,3}, u_{n,4}$ and assign the label 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $u_{n,5}, u_{n,6}, u_{n,7}, u_{n,8}$. Proceeding like this until we reach the vertex $u_{n,(m-3)}$ then finally assign the label 1, 2, 4 to the vertices $u_{n,(m-2)}, u_{n,(m-1)}, u_{n,m}$.

Subcase 2.15 $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}, m \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

As in Case 1 assign the label to the vertices $u_i, 1 \leq i \leq n-6$ and assign the label 1, 3, 2, 4, 2, 3 respectively to the vertices $u_{n-5}, u_{n-4}, u_{n-3}, u_{n-2}, u_{n-1}, u_n$. Next assign the labels to the vertices $u_{i,j}$ by

$$f(u_{i,j}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 1, } i = 1, 5, 9, \dots, n-5, \\ 2 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 3, } i = 2, 6, 10, \dots, n-3, \\ 3 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 2, } i = 3, 7, 11, \dots, n-4, \\ 4 & \text{if } u_i \text{ gets label 4, } i = 4, 8, 12, \dots, n-2. \end{cases}$$

Finally, assign the label 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $u_{(n-1),1}, u_{(n-1),2}, u_{(n-1),3}, u_{(n-1),4}$ and assign the label 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $u_{(n-1),5}, u_{(n-1),6}, u_{(n-1),7}, u_{(n-1),8}$. Proceeding like this until we reach the vertex $u_{(n-1),(m-3)}$ then finally assign the label 1, 2, 4 to the vertices $u_{(n-1),(m-2)}, u_{(n-1),(m-1)}, u_{(n-1),m}$. Finally assign the label 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $u_{n,1}, u_{n,2}, u_{n,3}, u_{n,4}$ and assign the label 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices $u_{n,5}, u_{n,6}, u_{n,7}, u_{n,8}$. Proceeding like this until we reach the vertex $u_{n,(m-3)}$ then finally assign the label 2, 4, 4 to the vertices $u_{n,(m-2)}, u_{n,(m-1)}, u_{n,m}$.

Subcase 2.16 $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}, m \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

As in Case 1 assign the label to the vertices u_i and $u_{i,j}$.

Thus, the Table 9 below shows that this vertex labeling gives the 4-remainder cordial labeling of caterpillar.

Nature of n	$v_f(1)$	$v_f(2)$	$v_f(3)$	$v_f(4)$	η_e	η_o
$n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-2}{2}$	$\frac{nm+n}{2}$
$n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-2}{2}$	$\frac{nm+n}{2}$
$n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{2}$	$\frac{nm+n-2}{2}$
$n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n}{4}$	$\frac{nm+n-2}{2}$	$\frac{nm+n+2}{2}$

Table 9

This completes the proof. \square

References

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